

The Generalized Atom-Bond Connectivity Index and Some Hamiltonian Properties of a Graph

Rao Li

Dept. of Computer Science, Engineering and Mathematics
University of South Carolina Aiken
Aiken, SC 29801
USA

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Abstract

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph. The generalized atom-bond connectivity index of a graph G is defined as $\sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u)+d(v)-2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha$, where α is a nonzero real number and $d(u)$ and $d(v)$ denote the degrees of vertices u and v in G , respectively. In this short note, we present sufficient conditions involving the generalized atom-bond connectivity index with $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$ for some Hamiltonian properties of a graph. We also present an upper bound for the generalized atom-bond connectivity index with $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$.

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1 Introduction

We consider only finite undirected graphs without loops or multiple edges. Notations and terminologies not defined here follow those in [1]. Let $G = (V(G), E(G))$ be a graph with n vertices and e edges, the degree of a vertex v in G is denoted by $d_G(v)$. We use $\delta(G)$ and $\Delta(G)$ to denote the minimum degree and maximum degree of G , respectively. The complement of a graph G is denoted by G^c . We use $G[S]$ to denote a subgraph of G induced by a subset S of V . A set of vertices in a graph G is independent if the vertices in the set are pairwise nonadjacent. A maximum independent set in a graph G is an independent set of largest possible size. The independence number, denoted $\beta(G)$, of a graph G is the cardinality of a maximum independent set in G . For disjoint vertex subsets X and Y of $V(G)$, we use $E(X, Y)$ to denote the set of all the edges in $E(G)$ such that one end vertex of each edge is in X and another end vertex of the edge is in Y . Namely, $E(X, Y) := \{ f : f = xy \in E, x \in X, y \in Y \}$. We use $G_1 \vee G_2$ to denote the the join of two disjoint graphs G_1 and G_2 . The complete graph of order p is denoted by K_p . A cycle C in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian cycle of G if C contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called Hamiltonian if G has a Hamiltonian cycle. A path P in a graph G is called a Hamiltonian path of G if P contains all the vertices of G . A graph G is called traceable if G has a Hamiltonian path.

A variety of topological indexes for graphs such as Wiener index [10], Randić index [8], and the first Zagreb index [7] have been introduced. In 1998, Estrada, Torres, Rodríguez, and Gutman [6] introduced the atom–bond connectivity index (ABC -index) of a graph G , denoted $ABC(G)$, which is defined as

$$ABC(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Furtula, Graovac, and Vukičević [5] extended the concept of the atom-bond connectivity index to the concept of the generalized atom-bond connectivity index, denoted $ABC_\alpha(G)$, which is defined as

$$ABC_\alpha(G) := \sum_{uv \in E} \left(\frac{d(u) + d(v) - 2}{d(u)d(v)} \right)^\alpha.$$

where α is nonzero real number. Obviously, $ABC_\alpha(G)$ becomes $ABC(G)$ when $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$. Some results on the generalized atom-bond connectivity index of a graph can be found in [2] [9] [4]. In this short note, we present sufficient conditions involving $ABC_\alpha(G)$ with $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$ for some Hamiltonian properties of a graph G . We also present an upper bound for $ABC_\alpha(G)$ with $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$ of a graph G . The main results are as follows.

Theorem 1. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices. If

$$\begin{aligned} ABC_\alpha(G) &\geq ABC_\alpha(K_{k+1}^c \vee K_{n-k-1}) \\ &= \frac{(k+1)(2n-k-4)^\alpha(n-k-1)^{1-\alpha}}{(n-1)^\alpha} + \frac{(n-k-1)(n-k-2)(2n-4)^\alpha}{2(n-1)^{2\alpha}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$, then G Hamiltonian or G is $K_{k+1}^c \vee K_k$.

Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph with n vertices. If

$$\begin{aligned} ABC_\alpha(G) &\geq ABC_\alpha(K_{k+2}^c \vee K_{n-k-2}) \\ &= \frac{(k+2)(2n-k-5)^\alpha(n-k-2)^{1-\alpha}}{(n-1)^\alpha} + \frac{(n-k-2)(n-k-3)(2n-4)^\alpha}{2(n-1)^{2\alpha}}, \end{aligned}$$

where $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$, then G traceable or G is $K_{k+2}^c \vee K_k$.

Theorem 3. Let G be a connected graph with n vertices and independence number $\beta \geq 2$. If $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} ABC_\alpha(G) &\leq ABC_\alpha(K_\beta^c \vee K_{n-\beta}) \\ &= \frac{\beta(2n-\beta-3)^\alpha(n-\beta)^{1-\alpha}}{(n-1)^\alpha} + \frac{(n-\beta)(n-\beta-1)(2n-4)^\alpha}{2(n-1)^{2\alpha}} \end{aligned}$$

with equality if and only if G is $K_\beta^c \vee K_{n-\beta}$.

2 Lemmas

We will use the following results as our lemmas. The first two are from [3].

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Lemma 1 [3]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order $n \geq 3$. If $\beta \leq k$, then G is Hamiltonian.

Lemma 2 [3]. Let G be a k -connected graph of order n . If $\beta \leq k + 1$, then G is traceable.

The last one is Theorem 3.1 on Page 119 in [2].

Lemma 3 [2]. Let G be a connected graph with nonadjacent vertices u and v . If $\frac{1}{2} \geq \alpha \neq 0$, then $ABC_\alpha(G + uv) > ABC_\alpha(G)$.

3 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 2$) graph with $n \geq 3$ vertices satisfying the conditions in Theorem 1. If each pair of vertices in G are adjacent, then G is Hamiltonian. Now we assume that there exist vertices x and y in G such that x and y are not adjacent in G . Suppose G is not Hamiltonian. Then Lemma 1 implies that $\beta \geq k + 1$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 1 \geq 2k + 1$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq n/2$ and G is Hamiltonian. Let $I_1 := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+1}\}$ is an independent set in G .

If there exist vertices $u \in I$ and $v \in V - I$ such that $uv \notin E$, we, from Lemma 3, have that

$$ABC_\alpha(G + uv) > ABC_\alpha(G) \geq ABC_\alpha(K_{k+1}^c \vee K_{n-k-1}) \geq ABC_\alpha(G + uv),$$

a contradiction. Thus $uv \in E$ for any $u \in I$ and any $v \in V - I$. If there exist two distinct vertices $u, v \in V - I$ such that $uv \notin E$, we, from Lemma 3, have that

$$ABC_\alpha(G + uv) > ABC_\alpha(G) \geq ABC_\alpha(K_{k+1}^c \vee K_{n-k-1}) \geq ABC_\alpha(G + uv),$$

a contradiction. Thus $uv \in E$ for any $u \in V - I$ and any $v \in V - I$, where $u \neq v$.

Notice that $|V - I| \leq |I| - 1$ otherwise G would be Hamiltonian. Thus $n - k - 1 \leq k$ and therefore $n \leq 2k + 1$. Since $n \geq 2k + 1$, we have that

$n = 2k + 1$. Thus G is $K_{k+1}^c \vee K_k$. Hence we complete the proof of Theorem 1.

The proof of Theorem 2 below is similar to the proof of Theorem 1 above. For the sake of the completeness, we still present the proof of Theorem 2 next.

Proof of Theorem 2. Let G be a k -connected ($k \geq 1$) graph with n vertices satisfying the conditions in Theorem 2. If each pair of vertices in G are adjacent, then G is traceable. Now we assume that there exist vertices x and y in G such that x and y are not adjacent in G . Suppose G is not traceable. Then Lemma 2 implies that $\beta \geq k + 2$. Also, we have that $n \geq 2\delta + 2 \geq 2k + 2$ otherwise $\delta \geq k \geq (n - 1)/2$ and G is traceable. Let $I_1 := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_\beta\}$ be a maximum independent set in G . Then $I := \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_{k+2}\}$ is an independent set in G .

If there exist vertices $u \in I$ and $v \in V - I$ such that $uv \notin E$, we, from Lemma 3, have that

$$ABC_\alpha(G + uv) > ABC_\alpha(G) \geq ABC_\alpha(K_{k+2}^c \vee K_{n-k-2}) \geq ABC_\alpha(G + uv),$$

a contradiction. Thus $uv \in E$ for any $u \in I$ and any $v \in V - I$. If there exist two distinct vertices $u, v \in V - I$ such that $uv \notin E$, we, from Lemma 3, have that

$$ABC_\alpha(G + uv) > ABC_\alpha(G) \geq ABC_\alpha(K_{k+2}^c \vee K_{n-k-2}) \geq ABC_\alpha(G + uv),$$

a contradiction. Thus $uv \in E$ for any $u \in V - I$ and any $v \in V - I$, where $u \neq v$.

Notice that $|V - I| \leq |I| - 2$ otherwise G would be traceable. Thus $n - k - 2 \leq k$ and therefore $n \leq 2k + 2$. Since $n \geq 2k + 2$, we have that $n = 2k + 2$. Thus G is $K_{k+2}^c \vee K_k$. Hence we complete the proof of Theorem 2.

The proof of Theorem 3 follows immediately from the proof of Theorem 1 or the proof of Theorem 2. A full proof of Theorem 3 is skipped here.

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